

Shiraz 21 nov . 1969

Dear Bill,

We got to Shiraz in one piece though I had to change a water pump on the car at Meymah. Linda was overjoyed at your present and thanks you profusely. Richard has been back in Shiraz for six weeks because he was ill but yesterday he went back to Hengam. His first stay there seems to have been successful. The kids are fine. I went to see Mrs Frye who is sweet but seems rather lonely, but her husband will be here in a month ^{she lives in the Neranistan.} I understand that the ~~peasant~~ peasants at Pasargadae have found a treasure now in Teheran. The Tillias have seen it and mention at third hand gold bowl(s). Jay and Soumi have got their money all but a bit and will probably be leaving in a week or so and after a bit in Isfahan will be through Teheran on the way to England and U.S.A. They are so much more relaxed! and hope to be back in the summer. Linda seems much less overburdened with her work than when I was last here though she still tutors at the moment, she is far from losing her sense of humour.

We spent a wet day in the Marv Dasht and despite my efforts Martha succeeded in finding several prehistoric sites of which details on the attached paper. We got to all the sites you had crossed and investigated hundreds of horrible high heaps besides, but it is an area with lots of natural mounds and we could well have missed some more. The pot and the maps are in a box awaiting transport to Teheran. We'd be interested to hear if our diagnosis of pottery is anything like correct. Sorry no painted ware.

Love from everyone here especially from Shirin to Willy

yours

Andy in haste (as usual)

P.S. In the basement of the Institute with the boiler in there is a gallon can of mine (an oil can) full of latex. I'd be very grateful if you could salvage it + put it with the rest of my things in the other basement. Also formally - the other basement is a greenish brown grey raincoat of

rather copy with 'le pottery + the map.

Marv Dasht survey 20 nov 1969

- 7 M 1 Main mound 110 by 70 m. separated by a joube from a small one 50 m. square. Hight on map.
Pottery: Bakun A 5 red ware, soft ware (of same period I presume)
one bevel rim bowl.
Present use gabristan.
- 7 M 2 Large series of mounds. Pottery: very sporadic Islamic 3. Present use cultivation.
- 7 M 3 Islamic 1 and 2. Qaleh morphology. Size and hight on map.
- 7 M 4 2 nasty sherds of Islamic 3 not kept.
- 7 M 5 80m. by 50m. Hight on map. Soft ware and lots of prehistoric crud.
- 7 M 6 100m. by 60m. Lots of pottery: some software and all sorts of fancy unpainted prehistoric rims (Kaftari?) some Bakun A 5 red ware and one ? bevel rim bowl.
- 7 M 7 Main mound 140 by 50m. mound 10 m. across just South had one sherd of Red Bakun A 5 ware. Pottery: Bad Bakun A 5 red ware and one bevel rim bowl as on almost every ~~previ~~ previous mound.
- 7 M 8 Baby mound 40m. square a ^{few} ~~few~~ pieces of crud c 75 cm ht
- 7 M 9 Few sherds of Islamic 3. Most of site has harabi wall stubs. Pot not kept

Where use of site at present not given present use =no use

where your crosses were visited and produced no pot they are hatched on the map. Sites are filled in in pencil, except for cross shading on 7.M.2.
agw. mep. with love

P.S in pottery markings M for Martha.